

Studies on CFD Analysis in Steam Nozzles - A Review

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Abstract

The nozzle is a device that guides the steam to hit the moving or rotating blades and to convert one form of energy into another i.e., to convert the pressure energy into kinetic energy. Within the case of a small turbine. The nozzle designs are improved depending upon the application where it is used and the factors considered for the design of the system. To examine and understand the performance of different types of nozzles, numerical simulations are done in a analysis software known as fluent. In this review, a literature study was conducted related to temperature, pressure, density, velocity, and power output parameters. In addition, a summary was provided related to the performance of the nozzles in turbines.

Keywords: Steam Nozzle, Convergent, Divergent, Convergent-Divergent, CFD.

1. INTRODUCTION

The cross-sectional (CS) area of a convergent nozzle (CN) decreases constantly from the start of the nozzle to the end of the nozzle. Convergent Nozzle is utilized when the rear pressure is greater than or equal to the critical pressure ratio. From the start to the end of the nozzle, the cross-sectional area of a diverging nozzle grows continually. It's used in situations where the critical pressure is more than the rear pressure. The cross-sectional (CS) area of a Convergent-Divergent Nozzle reduces from the beginning of the nozzle to the throat, then grows from throat to mouth.

Computer Fluid Dynamics(CFD) is an engineering tool that aids in experimentation. CFD's tools utilized not only in fluid dynamics but it is also used in many processes that involve transport phenomena. We can utilize a variety of approaches to tackle an engineering problem, such as experimental methods and analytical methods using prototypes. The process of analysis is quite complex. The experimental procedures are extremely expensive. Suppose if any errors have occurred during the process, then we need to recreate a completely new prototype which solves all the problems and is tested again. It consumes both time and money. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has solved this problem while also

revolutionizing the world of engineering. CFD involves simulating a problem in software and solving the problem's transport equations mathematically with the aid of a computer. As a result, we would be able to predict the outcome of an issue before attempting to solve it. Steps involved in Computational Fluid Dynamics are: Modeling, Meshing, and Pre-Processing

The ejector is a device that uses a CN to increase the water velocity to convert large static pressure into velocity pressure. The entrainment ratio (E.R.) is a global parameter generally used to evaluate the performance of the ejector system.

2. PREVIOUS STUDIES ON VARIOUS STEAM NOZZLES

Simpson and White [1], reported the results of 2D calculations for instantaneous nucleating steam flow in a CD nozzle are presented in this work. An increase of the boundary layer (BL) has a considerable effect on projected pressure variations and droplet shape and sizes, according to the viscous calculations done for a flow in a CD nozzle at steady conditions, at least in circumstances where two-dimensional effects are dominant. In Asymmetric mode of swinging, has been observed before in moist airflow, occur in steam as well, according to unsteady, non-viscous calculations for different types of nozzle shapes.

Aravind et al. [2] studied the simulation of a steam ejector's operation to increase performance. For the similar superheat, evaporator temp., and pressure conditions in the condenser, entrainment ratio (E.R.) increases as the boiler saturation temperature decreases and also increases with the rise in evaporator pressure. As the throat diameter becomes less, the Entrainment ratio becomes high as compared to the earlier values.

Pujowidodo et al. [3] investigated the effect of mass flow of the steam on a Curved CD Nozzle using the analytical solution and CFD modelling. The goal of the study was to compare the results of thermodynamics analysis and turbulent model simulation with solutions characteristics from the solution and also the flow properties from the solution. To calculate the mass flow of steam, the Computational fluid dynamics post analysis tool is used which includes the steps such as integrating velocity across the flow section.

Dura [4] studied the condensation of superheated water-vapor in a supersonic Barschdorff nozzle using Ansys 2 phase steady and unsteady, non-equilibrium condensation flow model of the steam, the effect or impact of pneumatic mounts in a 3D Laval nozzle was investigated. The conservation of mass, conservation of momentum, and conservation of energy of the entire system connects variables that constitute two-phase flow. A traditional

homogeneous nucleation theory describes the production of droplets. The boundary layer has a substantial impact close to the pipe and as well the wall. There is a possibility of being in all the three directions near the pipe. Findings of a 3D simulation are compared to the results of a 2D simulation. The blade's structural health is harmed by this force of unstable condensation. The nucleation model's correction factor 'f' is depending on the condition given at the boundary and shape of the nozzle and so does not have a fixed value.

Pennaturu and Issac [5] studied the performance of a utility Steam Turbine Module using CFD research. The efficiency of energy conversion and the analysis of motion of the fluid behavior in the different parts of the Steam Turbine determine turbine's performance. CFD study of the turbine flow path assists in the analysis of flow and performance parameters, as well as the implications of these parameters on performance metrics such as temperature, pressure, and power output. The Intermediate Pressure turbine module's CFD analysis was useful in predicting turbine performance and comparing it to experimentally verified values. The results are compared to a two-dimensional program that has been empirically evaluated and found to agree with the two-dimensional analysis.

Madhu et al. [6] reported the flow parameters of a supersonic nozzle at various divergence angles. The area of a converging section is believed to be constant, but the area of a diverging section changes with respect to the divergence angle. The validation of numerical findings shows that acceptable results can be obtained even when the computational region is restricted to the nozzle exit. When comparing contour nozzles to conical nozzles with the same end geometry, higher levels of turbulence and separation of the fluid is detected and have greater Mach numbers at the exit for diverging angles at all positions.

Azimian and Bart [7] reported the effects of ingested steam flow, including solid particles, on the radial inflow turbine on its blades were studied in depth. Furthermore, erosion modeling findings revealed that considerable erosion occurs in three main surface areas. The end edge of the stationary blade, with a large number of particles with sharp-edged angles that impact the surface, is the only largest affected area across-section of the investigated steam turbine of radial size. The starting edge of the rotor blade which is present on the suction side, where the impact of the particles takes place numerous times, is the second but less affected section. The center portion of the rotor blade on the pressure side is the third surface area that has been extensively degraded.

Sharma et al. [8] explored the various cross-sections of the converging-diverging nozzles, such as rectangle, square, and circle, which affect the flow properties by using

Computational Fluid Dynamics and determine which gives maximum velocity at the outlet. After analysis in Ansys fluent, the contours for temperature, velocity, and pressure are compared, and it found that a rectangular cross-section gives better results when compared to others.

Jilani&Phaneendra [9] analysed the different types of nozzles, namely the Moore, Moses, and CD nozzle, for which velocity, pressure, temperatures, and erosion rate were determined. When compared to other nozzles, the rate of erosion in the Moore nozzle is the least, and the velocity at the exit is the lowest. The CD Nozzle has highest outlet velocity and the lowest erosion rate. In the end, the convergent-divergent nozzle was found to be the most favorable of all the nozzles.

Ruangtrakoon et al. [10] investigated the performance of an ejector in a steam jet refrigeration cycle under the influence of primary nozzle geometries using CFD. In each of the situations, a single fixed-geometry mixing chamber was used in conjunction with eight distinct main nozzles for the purpose of doing a numerical investigation utilising the commercial CFD software package known as FLUENT 6.3. We observed and examined the impact that these changes had on the primary fluid's pressure as well as the mass flow rate and Mach number. In order to describe the mixing process that was taking place within the ejector, the Mach number contour lines were utilised. It was discovered that the shock's position of the mixed fluid and the expansion angle of the primary fluid jet stream within the mixing chamber had a very essential part in the ejector's overall effectiveness. Both of these factors may be located within the mixing chamber.

Wasie and Getnet [11] analyzed the flow pattern of supersonic, sonic, and subsonic nozzles using CFD. The goal of the article is to investigate the behavior of flow in a CD and throat section nozzle with the help of CFD software to examine various variables such as pressure(P), temperature(T), density, and velocity(V) in order to obtain the maximum velocity at the exit of the nozzle. The pressure(P) is highest in convergent part and lowest in the divergent section. Velocity increases as the area increases, with the highest velocity at the exit. We may deduce that by keeping the convergent angle constant, we can attain the greatest velocity at a greater divergent angle of a nozzle.

Gulawani et al. [12] investigated the direct contact steam condensation, which is utilised in steam jet injectors and direct contact feed water heaters using CFD simulation. With the available experimental data of plume length and the profiles of axial and radial temperature, a very good agreement has been established. In addition, a careful analysis of each and every

published semi-empirical model and correlation has been carried out. In addition, the CFD study has been expanded to investigate the effect of the nozzle diameter and geometry, both of which have a bearing on the heat transfer phenomena that is the primary driver of the phenomenon of direct contact steam condensation. A new hydrodynamic model has been developed, and one of its functions is to calculate the amount of interfacial area that is open to condensation. There has been the development of a reasonable correlation for the calculation of the interfacial area, which has been stated in terms of the Nusselt number (Nu), the Reynolds number (Re), the Prandtl number (Pr), and the ratio of the viscosity of steam and water.

3. CONCLUSION

As a result, from the literature review discussed above, the different areas that will be covered in this study are as follows:

- Analysis of steam nozzles, both convergent and divergent
- Design and analysis of steam turbine nozzles.
- In Curved CD Nozzle, the saturated steam flow rate of the mass is calculated.
- Unsteady flow and non-equilibrium condensation behavior in steam nozzles.
- Performance of nozzles in steam turbines
- Steam ejector with different nozzle diameter.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Simpson, D. A., & White, A. J. (2005). Viscous and unsteady flow calculations of condensing steam in nozzles. *International journal of heat and fluid flow*, 26(1), 71-79.
- [2] Aravind, T., Reddy, P. R., & Baserkoed, S. S. (2014). Thermal Analysis of Steam Ejector Using CFD. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 3, 18311-18318.
- [3] Pujowidodo, H., Siswantara, A. I., Daryus, A., & Gunadi, G. G. R. (2019, January). The analytic and CFD modeling studies of saturated steam mass flow in curved convergent divergent nozzle. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2062, No. 1, p. 020015). AIP Publishing LLC.

- [4] Dura, H. B. (2019). Numerical Investigation of a Steam Nozzle with Focus on Non-Equilibrium Condensation and Unsteady Flow Behavior. *Journal of the Institute of Engineering*, 15(1), 25-36.
- [5] Pennaturu, S., & Issac, P. (2014). Evaluating performance of steam turbine using CFD. *Int. J. Latest Trends Eng. Technol*, 4, 209-304.
- [6] Madhu, B. P., Mahendramani, G., & Bhaskar, K. (2021). Numerical analysis on flow properties in convergent–Divergent nozzle for different divergence angle. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 45, 207-215.
- [7] Azimian, M., & Bart, H. J. (2016). Computational analysis of erosion in a radial inflow steam turbine. *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 64, 26-43.
- [8] Sharma, N. K., Kumar, A., Sharma, A., Singh, B. P., & Tyagi, C. (2020). CFD Analysis of Convergent-Divergent Nozzle. *Aegaeum Journal*, 8 (6), 1359-1372.
- [9] Jilani, S. A. & Phaneendra, V. CVS., (2021) Design and Analysis of Steam Turbine Nozzle, *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 8(3), 1162-1166.
- [10] Ruangtrakoon, N., Thongtip, T., Aphornratana, S., & Sriveerakul, T. (2013). CFD simulation on the effect of primary nozzle geometries for a steam ejector in refrigeration cycle. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 63, 133-145.
- [11] Wasie, T. & Getnet, T (2021). Design and Analysis of Fluid Flow in Convergent-Divergent nozzle using ANSYS Fluent Software, *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science*, 9(10), 61-76.
- [12] Gulawani, S. S., Joshi, J. B., Shah, M. S., Rama Prasad, C. S., & Shukla, D. S. (2006). CFD analysis of flow pattern and heat transfer in direct contact steam condensation. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 61(16), 5204-5220.